

Assessing the Influence of Digital Learning Tools on Students' Practical Skills Acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology Programme in Polytechnics in Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed the influence of digital learning tools on students' practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State. Practical instructions are being supported by the increasing incorporation of digital learning tools for competence development; however, the extent to which these tools influence students' practical skills acquisition remains unclear in Rivers State. This is the gap the study intends to fill. The study was guided by 2 objectives, 2 research questions and 2 hypotheses. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population of the study was 42, which comprised of 30 Lecturers and 12 Technologists. The sample size was 42, using census sampling technique. The instrument for the study was a structured questionnaire, used to collect data from Lecturers and Technologists in Rivers State government owned polytechnics offering Electrical/Electronic Engineering/Technology programmes. The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by 3 experts from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. Reliability indices of the instrument was determined using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.81; indicating good consistency. The instrument used a five-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE=5), High Extent (HE=4), Moderate Extent (ME=3), Low Extent (LE=2) and Very Low Extent (VLE=1). 3.0 criterion mean was used. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while z-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance tested the hypotheses. Findings revealed that digital learning tools have strong positive influence on students' practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State. It was recommended that Government and school management should enhance ICT infrastructure by providing reliable internet connectivity, stable power supply (including backup systems like solar inverters), and well-equipped ICT centres accessible to students.

Keywords: Assessing, Influence, Digital, Learning, Tools, Students, Practical, Skills, Acquisition

INTRODUCTION

Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) is a system of education that is strategically designed to equip learners with practical skills, technical competencies and occupational knowledge for effective participation in the world of work. It emphasizes the acquisition of hands-on abilities, problem-solving capacity and technological proficiency tailored to industry demands. According to United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) [2022], TVET encompasses educational processes that involve the study of technologies and related sciences, as well as the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes and understanding relevant to various sectors of economic and social life. It plays a transformative role in national development by promoting employability, entrepreneurship and innovation, thereby contributing significantly to industrial growth and economic sustainability (Oviawe et al., 2017). Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) play a crucial role in national development, industrial growth, and workforce preparation. Globally, TVET systems are designed to

equip learners with the practical competencies, technical know-how, and problem-solving skills required for employment, entrepreneurship, and technological advancement (Umar & Aliyu, 2020). In Nigeria, TVET is recognized as a major driver for producing middle-level manpower needed to support sectors such as manufacturing, construction, power, telecommunication, oil and gas, and emerging technology fields. Consequently, institutions such as polytechnics are mandated to produce graduates with strong practical competencies and industry-relevant skills.

In Nigeria, polytechnics occupy a central position within the TVET framework as tertiary institutions, mandated to produce skilled manpower equipped for technological innovation and industrial advancement. They operate under competency-based standards designed to bridge the gap between theoretical learning and practical application, making them uniquely positioned to address national needs for technologically proficient graduates [National Board for Technical Education (NBTE), 2020]. Unlike conventional higher institutions that prioritize abstract knowledge, polytechnics emphasize

applied learning through structured curricula that incorporate laboratory activities, workshop practices and industrial training as compulsory elements of instruction (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). This practical orientation ensures that students develop the technical abilities, analytical thinking and hands-on proficiency necessary to function effectively in workplaces driven by technology and digital systems (Akinyemi & Abiodun, 2021). In alignment to national economic objectives, polytechnics are tasked with promoting industrial development, fostering self-reliance and enhancing employment readiness by producing graduates who can adapt to evolving technological demands. Polytechnics programmes are carefully organized into specialized departments that cater to distinct areas of technological practice; each tailored to building professional competence in a specific occupational discipline. These programmes function as the core academic units through which the practical and technical mandate of the polytechnic is actualized, and they include disciplines such as Electrical/Electronic Technology, Mechanical Technology, Computer Technology among others.

Electrical/Electronic Technology is a branch of engineering and TVET that focuses on the study, design, construction, operation, maintenance, and troubleshooting of electrical and electronic systems. It combines the principles of electricity, electronics and electromagnetism with practical skills to equip students with the knowledge and competence to handle devices, circuits, and systems in residential, commercial, industrial, and communication applications (Hambley, 2011). Electrical/Electronic Technology as a programme studied in the polytechnics, is central to Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) because it produces skilled technicians and technologists who meet the demands of modern industries, infrastructure, and technological innovation. It emphasizes hands-on training in electrical installations, power systems, electronics fabrication, circuit design, instrumentation, communication systems, and equipment maintenance. Practical skills training involves learning to use tools and instruments such as multimeters, oscilloscopes, soldering irons, programmable controllers, and diagnostic equipment. Traditionally, these skills are acquired through workshop practice, laboratory experiments, demonstration lessons, and supervised industrial training (Dorf & Svoboda, 2014). However, over the last decade, the rapid advancement of digital technology has introduced new possibilities for improving the teaching and learning process in TVET institutions through practical skills acquisition emphases.

Practical skills in Electrical/Electronic Technology refer to the hands-on, applied abilities that enable students or

practitioners to implement, test, troubleshoot, maintain, and optimize electrical and electronic systems. These skills are essential for translating theoretical knowledge into real-world applications, ensuring that learners can safely and effectively handle equipment, tools, and circuits (Ajuluchukwu & Nwosu, 2018). In Technical and Vocational Education, practical skills are the cornerstone of competence and modern technology. This is because Electrical/Electronic Technology involves working with live circuits, electrical machines, electronic devices, and control systems. It emphasises students' acquisition of practical skills that will enable them to construct, test, operate, troubleshoot, and maintain electrical and electronic systems safely and effectively. Students Practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology is an essential means to producing competent graduates capable of meeting industrial, commercial, and technological demands (Isa, 2024). Skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology is the systematic development of cognitive, psychomotor, safety, problem-solving, and digital competencies required to perform electrical and electronic tasks effectively. It involves hands-on practice, guided instruction, digital simulations, and exposure to real-world systems. However, Adebayo and Kareem (2017) found out that TVET students like those in polytechnics don't acquire adequate practical skills in Electrical/Electronic Technology while in school. Similarly, National Directorate of Employment (NDE) [2016] reported; practical skills acquisition of polytechnic students in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme is poor for a work life. The report emphasized; the problem of poor practical skills acquisition in polytechnics is becoming a menace to the society. Robinson (2017) added, poor practical skills acquisition of Electrical/Electronic Technology students in polytechnics is affecting technological advancement in Nigeria. But several authors are of the view that poor student's practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics is linked to poor use of digital learning tools in the workshop.

Digital learning is the integration of technology, multimedia, and online platforms to deliver, support, and enhance teaching and learning. In technical and vocational education, particularly in Electrical/Electronic Technology, digital learning enables students to acquire theoretical knowledge, develop practical skills, and engage in safe simulated experimentation. When effectively implemented, it complements traditional teaching methods, improves learning outcomes, and prepares students for modern industrial and technological environments (Redecker, 2017). However, tools that are used in digital learning are referred to as digital learning tools. Digital learning

tools are technological resources, software, and applications used to facilitate, enhance, and support the teaching and learning processes. These tools provide opportunities for learners to acquire knowledge, develop practical skills, interact with instructional content, collaborate with peers, and receive feedback in a digital environment (Olawale & Opaleye, 2020). In technical and vocational education, such as Electrical/Electronic Technology, digital learning tools are essential for bridging the gap between theoretical concepts and hands-on practice. They encompass technological resources that facilitate learning by providing interactive, multimedia, and simulation-based experiences. In Electrical/Electronic Technology education, they enable students to acquire practical skills safely, efficiently, and effectively. By complementing traditional workshop practice, digital learning tools enhance skill acquisition, improve conceptual understanding, and prepare students for modern industry demands. The successful implementation of these tools depends on availability, accessibility, proper training, and institutional support. Digital learning tools can be categorized broadly into hardware tools, software tools and online tools that can support both theoretical learning and practical skills acquisition (Anderson, 2008). Hardware tools are physical devices that enable access to digital learning resources. Examples are computers, smartphones, smartboards, projectors and specialized technical devices. Software tools are functional software applications necessary for learning and skill development. Examples are circuit simulation software, computer-aided design (CAD) software, learning management systems (LMS) software programming and microcontroller software and multimedia authoring software. Online tools are web-based platforms that support content delivery, interaction, collaboration, and assessment. Examples are virtual laboratories, instructional videos and tutorials, collaborative platforms, assessment tools and educational apps. These tools offer learners opportunities to visualize complex technical concepts, practice procedures repeatedly without risk, and experiment with designs before implementing them physically.

In Nigeria, polytechnics particularly in Rivers State are gradually integrating digital learning technologies into instructional delivery due to increased access to mobile devices, government initiatives promoting ICT integration, and the need to modernize TVET training. However, there is ongoing debate about whether digital learning tools can genuinely strengthen practical skills acquisition, especially in fields that require physical manipulation, precision, and tactile experience like Electrical/Electronic Technology programme. Clark and Mayer (2016) and Okwelle (2013), opined that proper

use of digital learning tools in the workshop, positively influences students' practical skills acquisition. They emphasised, in technical fields such as Electrical/Electronic Technology, digital learning tools provide opportunities for students to acquire more practical skills. But West, et.al. (2017) and Yakubu and Musa (2022), decried that the use of digital learning tools in the workshop does not necessarily influence students' practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme when there are other constraining factors.

Contextually, influence refers to the effect, impact, or power that one variable, factor, or phenomenon exerts on another. It describes the degree to which the use of digital learning tools changes students' practical skills acquisition. The divergent opinions over the influence of digital learning tools on students' practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics was the rationale behind the researchers' interest on this study "Assessing the influence of digital learning tools on students' practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State". Given these realities, there is a need for a systematic assessment of how digital learning tools influence the acquisition of practical skills among students in Electrical/Electronic Technology programmes in polytechnics in Rivers State. In this context, assessment refers to the systematic process of collecting, analyzing, and interpreting information about learners, programs, tools, or practices to make informed judgments about their effectiveness, performance, progress, or outcomes. At the end, the findings of this study will provide valuable insights for curriculum developers, polytechnic administrators, lecturers, and policymakers seeking to enhance TVET delivery.

Statement of the Problem

Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET), particularly Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics, is designed to equip students with practical competencies required for employment and technological advancement. However, in recent years, many polytechnics in Rivers State have continued to struggle with the problem of poor students' practical skills acquisition (NDE, 2016; Robinson, 2017). This problem often reduces students' opportunities for meaningful hands-on practice, resulting in graduates who lack the level of technical proficiency expected by industries. Several authors are of the view that poor student's practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics is linked to poor use of digital learning tools in the workshop. These tools are expected to help students visualise electrical/electronic concepts, rehearse

procedures before physical practice. Despite their increasing availability globally, it remains unclear to what extent these tools are being integrated into teaching and learning practices in Rivers State polytechnics, and whether they actually contribute to improving practical skills acquisition among students.

This situation raises critical questions: Are digital learning tools being effectively utilized in polytechnics in Rivers State? Do these tools enhance students' practical skills or merely support theoretical understanding? What challenges hinder their adoption and effectiveness? Without evidence-based answers to these issues, efforts to modernize Electrical/Electronic Technology education may remain ineffective, and students may continue to graduate with insufficient practical competencies. Therefore, this study seeks to assess the influence of digital learning tools on students' practical skills acquisition in the Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State, with a view to identifying gaps, strengths, and areas for improvement.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to assess the influence of digital learning tools on students' practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State. The study specifically sought to determine:

1. the extent to which software tools influence students' practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State.
2. the extent to which hardware tools influence students' practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the extent to which software tools influence students' practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State?
2. What is the extent to which hardware tools influence students' practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Hypothesis 1 (H₀₁): There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Lecturers and Technologists

on the extent to which software tools influence students' practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2 (H₀₂): There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Lecturers and Technologists on the extent to which hardware tools influence students' practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which was considered appropriate because it enabled the researcher to collect opinions and observations from respondents without manipulating any variable. The population of the study was 42, comprised of 30 Lecturers and 12 Technologists from the department of Electrical/Electronic Technology in Rivers State owned polytechnics. They were Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic and Kenule Beeson Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic. The study used census sampling technique to obtain the sample size, since the population was manageable. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled Assessment of Digital Learning Tools Questionnaire (ADLTQ). The questionnaire used a five-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE=5), High Extent (HE=4), Moderate Extent (ME=3), Low Extent (LE=2) and Very Low Extent (VLE=1). The criterion mean was 3.0.

The research instrument was subjected to face and content validity through 3 experts from departments of measurement and evaluation, and electrical/electronic technology. A pilot test was carried out in Niger Delta University (NDU) Amassoma, Bayelsa State, which was not part of the study. The reliability of the instrument was determined using the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, with a threshold of 0.85 as acceptable. Data collected for the study were analyzed using mean to answer the research questions and standard deviation to determine the homogeneity or otherwise the variability of the responses. z-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Where the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05, the null hypotheses is rejected; but if the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypotheses is accepted.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What is the extent to which software tools influence students' practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean Scores of Software tools on Students’ Practical Skills Acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology Programme in Polytechnics in Rivers State.

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Lecturers (N=30)			Technologists (N=12)		
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	RMK	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	RMK
1.	Computer-aided design (CAD) software help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.53	0.51	HE	3.67	0.65	HE
2.	Programming software help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.47	0.57	HE	3.25	0.45	HE
3.	Circuit simulation software help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme?	3.43	0.50	HE	3.50	0.67	HE
4.	Learning management systems (LMS) software help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.03	0.18	HE	3.08	0.29	HE
5.	Multimedia authoring software help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.10	0.48	HE	3.00	0.00	HE
6.	Social media software help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.53	0.51	HE	3.17	0.39	HE
7.	Cloud computing software help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.43	0.50	HE	3.33	0.49	HE
8.	Data analysis software help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.20	0.41	HE	3.08	0.29	HE
9.	Computer application software help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.50	0.51	HE	3.00	0.00	HE
10.	Live communication software help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.07	0.25	HE	3.00	0.00	HE
Grand Mean		3.33	0.44	HE	3.21	0.32	HE

Result from Table 1 shows that Lecturers have a grand mean of 3.33 which indicates a High Extent (HE), and a standard deviation of 0.44. Similarly, from same table 1, Technologists have a grand mean of 3.21 which also indicates a High Extent (HE), and a standard deviation of 0.32. This revealed that both Lecturers and Technologists are of the opinion that influence of software tools on students’ practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State is of High Extent (HE).

However, the standard deviation of 0.44 and 0.32 for Lecturers and Technologists respectively shows that respondents’ opinions were closely grouped around the mean, showing high agreement or homogeneity of respondents.

Research Question 2: What is the extent to which hardware tools influence students’ practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean Scores of Hardware Tools on Students’ Practical skills Acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology Programme in Polytechnics in Rivers State.

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Lecturers (N=30)			Technologists (N=12)		
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	Rmk	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	Rmk
1.	Digital multimeters (DMM) help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.70	0.54	HE	3.58	0.52	HE
2.	Laptop computers help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.40	0.56	HE	3.25	0.45	HE
3.	Smartphones help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.03	0.18	HE	3.00	0.00	HE
4.	Digital tablets help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.50	0.57	HE	3.00	0.00	HE
5.	Interactive whiteboards help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.63	0.56	HE	3.58	0.52	HE
6.	Smartboards help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.10	0.40	HE	3.00	0.00	HE
7.	Projectors help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.63	0.56	HE	3.58	0.52	HE
8.	Programmable chips help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.53	0.57	HE	3.25	0.45	HE
9.	Digital oscilloscopes help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.03	0.18	HE	3.08	0.29	HE
10.	Digital Televisions help students’ practical skills acquisition in electrical/electronic technology programme	3.40	0.56	HE	3.00	0.00	HE
	Grand Mean	3.40	0.47	HE	3.23	0.28	HE

Result from Table 2 shows that Lecturers have a grand mean of 3.40 which indicates a High Extent (HE), and a standard deviation of 0.47. Similarly, from same table 2, Technologists have a grand mean of 3.23 which also indicates a High Extent (HE), and a standard deviation of 0.28. This revealed that both Lecturers and Technologists are of the opinion that influence of hardware tools on students’ practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State is of a High Extent (HE). However, the standard deviation of 0.47 and 0.28 for

Lecturers and Technologists respectively shows that respondents’ opinions were closely grouped around the mean, showing high agreement or homogeneity of respondents.

Hypothesis 1 (H₀₁): There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Lecturers and Technologists on the extent to which software tools influence students’ practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State.

Table 3: Z-test Analysis of Software Tools Influence on Students’ Practical Skills Acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology Programme in Polytechnics in Rivers State

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	A	Standard Error	z-cal.	z-crit	Decision
Lecturers	30	3.33	0.44	40	0.05	0.12	1.00	±2.02	Accepted
Technologists	12	3.21	0.32						

Result from Table 3 shows that Z-calculated value (1.00) is less than Z-critical value (2.02) at 0.05 level of significance, which indicates that hypothesis 1 was accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of Lecturers and Technologists on the extent to which software tools influence students’ practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State. This revealed that both Lecturers and Technologists are

of the opinion that software tools influence students’ practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State. **Hypothesis 2 (H₀₂):** There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Lecturers and Technologists on the extent to which hardware tools influence students’ practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State.

Table 4: Z-test Analysis of Hardware Tools Influence on Students’ Practical Skills Acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology Programme in Polytechnics in Rivers State.

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	A	Standard Error	z-cal.	z-crit	Decision
Lecturers	30	3.40	0.47	40	0.05	0.12	1.42	±2.02	Accepted
Technologists	12	3.23	0.23						

Result from Table 4 shows that z-calculated value (1.42) is less than z-critical value (2.02) at 0.05 level of significance, which indicates that hypothesis 2 was accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of Lecturers and Technologists on the extent to which hardware tools influence students’ practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State. This revealed that both Lecturers and Technologists are of the opinion that hardware tools influence students’ practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The study assessed the influence of digital learning tools on students’ practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State. The findings are discussed in line with the research objectives and relevant literature. From research question 1, the study showed that both Lecturers and Technologists are of the opinion that influence of software tools on students’ practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State was a High Extent (HE). Similarly, from hypothesis 1, the study showed that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of Lecturers and Technologists on the extent to which software tools influence students’ practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State.

These findings revealed that both Lecturers and Technologists are of the opinion that digital learning tools have strong positive influence on students’ practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State. But the pending problem of poor practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics reflects an existing gap. This could be because of other factors like; shortages of functioning equipment, large student-to-machine ratios, inconsistent electricity, and constrained budgets can hamper hands-on training. These findings agree with West, et.al. (2017), who reported that digital learning tools enhance conceptual understanding of practical skills, when other constraining factors are removed in the workshop. The present study therefore contributes location-specific evidence from Rivers State to this ongoing debate.

From research question 2, the study showed that both Lecturers and Technologists are of the opinion that influence of hardware tools on students’ practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State is of a High Extent (HE). Similarly, in hypothesis 2, the study showed that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of Lecturers and Technologists on the extent to which hardware tools influence students’

practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State. These findings revealed that both Lecturers and Technologists are of the opinion that digital learning tools have strong positive influence on students' practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State. In essence, in Rivers State polytechnics, the degree to which digital learning tools actually influence acquisition of practical skills remain certain if there are no other constraining factors in the workshops. These findings agree with Yakubu and Musa (2022), who emphasized the role of embedded systems in promoting creativity and system-level thinking in technical programs. Although earlier studies in the problem statement observed weak practical transfer, the present findings demonstrate that, within Rivers State polytechnics, these tools exert a measurable, though not uniform, influence on students' electrical/ electronic practical skills acquisition.

CONCLUSION

The study assessed the influence of digital learning tools on students' practical skills acquisition in the Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State. Based on the findings, the study concluded that digital learning tools have strong positive influence on students' practical skills acquisition in Electrical/Electronic Technology programme in polytechnics in Rivers State. It reflects the fact that, digital learning tools play a significant and positive role in enhancing students' understanding of technical concepts, improving their confidence during practical tasks, and supporting their overall competence in electrical/electronic operations. These tools help bridge gaps created by limited workshop equipment and large class sizes by offering alternative platforms for simulation, visualization, and repeated practice. Indeed, digital learning tools are valuable complements, not replacements to physical practical training in

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Electrical/Electronic Technology programmes. Strengthening their availability, effective utilization, and integration into instructional practices will significantly enhance students' practical competencies and better prepare them for industry demands in Rivers State and beyond.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The management of polytechnics in Rivers State should invest in acquiring updated modern digital software tools such as computer-aided design (CAD) software, multimedia authoring software, learning management systems (LMS), cloud computing software and programming software to support practical training in Electrical/Electronic Technology.
2. Lecturers should be given continuous professional development opportunities focused on digital pedagogy as it relates to the use of software tools on emerging technologies relevant to practical skills training.
3. Curriculum planners and departmental boards should incorporate digital hardware tools as mandatory components of practical courses, ensuring that simulation activities, multimedia resources, and online tasks are formally included in lesson plans and assessments.
4. Students should be encouraged to use digital hardware tools regularly through assignments, project work, and guided self-learning activities that require the engagement of practical skills learning.
5. The government and school management should enhance ICT infrastructure by providing reliable internet connectivity, stable power supply (including backup systems like solar inverters), and well-equipped ICT centres accessible to students.

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